

Literature Review on Methods in the Treatment of OCD

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Abstract

The efficacy of SSRIs in the treatment of OCD has been confirmed by research conducted by the Cochrane Collaboration, (Citalopram (Celexa) and escitalopram (Lexapro) are also widely used, but in 2011 the FDA began recommending dosage restrictions for citalopram due to concerns about QT prolongation. The alternative provided because there is little data to prove that an SSRI is superior It is important to personalize the dosage of SSRIs to consider possible adverse reactions as well as combinations with other drugs. Patients with OCD need to take higher doses of SSRIs than patients with other diseases to achieve best response After four to six weeks, the dose needs to be increased until the largest dose is reached Various adverse consequences, including serotonin syndrome There are cases where typical maximum dosages are used but carefully checked. A clinical trial of the drug is over a period of eight to twelve weeks at the highest reality should be paired. should expect to see a significant improvement in their symptoms after at least four to six weeks of treatment, although for some patients this may take ten or longer. To start with, there's the standard price, followed by the brand's price in parentheses. If it turns out that the patient needs a larger dose, electrocardiography and other tests should be performed on them to evaluate electrolytes and other substances. It is fair to aim

for relapse prevention with continuing SSRI drugs as the therapeutic goal. It may take longer for patients to feel the effects of psychological therapy than to the effects of medications. Regular exposure and response prevention sessions are recommended to reduce the likelihood of relapse after psychological treatment is stopped. If a trial of a proper SSRI or psychological treatment does not result in an acceptable response, combination therapy is an alternative that may be considered. If the patient decides to continue medical therapy on his own, it is recommended to try a different SSRI. If the patient does not show any improvement after at least two different SSRI treatment attempts, the patient should be referred to a psychiatrist. In these people, clomipramine is a potential treatment choice. It is recommended to start clomipramine at a low dose (25 mg daily) with slow titration to reduce unpleasant reactions. This is because clomipramine can produce anticholinergic side effects and, in rare cases, arrhythmias or seizures. Some people who do not respond well to SSRI treatment benefit from the addition of an atypical antipsychotic, which is beneficial. There is no consensus on which atypical antipsychotic drug is most effective, and the increased likelihood of causing side effects outweighs its benefits. There are several added options for patients with treatment-resistant OCD; however, the evidence for most treatments is weak.

Keywords: *OCD, Obsessive Compulsive Disorder, OCD Treatment, OCD Treatment Methods*

1. Introduction

Mirtazapine (Remeron) and serotonin-norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors have been shown in some studies to be effective treatments for obsessive - compulsive disorder (OCD). Glutamatergic agents, stimulants, pindolol , ondansetron (Zofran), acetylcysteine , and anticonvulsants are some of the other classes of drugs currently being investigated as potential treatments for epilepsy. Some encouraging findings have been reported in the case of severe Treatment-resistant OCD; however, these results have been evaluated in a limited number of individuals. This treatment is reserved for patients who have exhausted all other options and has been granted limited FDA clearance under the human device exemption. Women who suffered from obsessive -compulsive disorder before becoming pregnant may have worsening symptoms during pregnancy and have an increased chance of developing postpartum depression. Postpartum OCD may manifest as obsessive thoughts of harming the baby;

however, mothers suffering from this condition do not pose a significant danger to their children. Cognitive behavioral therapy as the treatment of choice for OCD during pregnancy and the postpartum period is indicated .

2. SSRI Medications During Pregnancy and Breastfeeding

When considering SSRI medications during pregnancy and breastfeeding, it's important to talk about performing an individual risk-benefit analysis. One to two percent of children in the United States are affected by obsessive -compulsive disorder (OCD), and fifty percent of these children also have other mental disorders. In mild to moderate cases, the first treatment of choice is exposure and response prevention cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT). Patients experiencing severe symptoms or comorbid mental illness are candidates for treatment with SSRIs in addition to CBT. CBT participation. In the treatment of pediatric OCD, cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) with or without medication is preferred to drug therapy alone.

3. Obsessive-Compulsive Symptoms in Children

obsessive -compulsive symptoms in children may be of concern in the context of pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric diseases due to streptococcal infection (PANDAS). The name PANDAS is becoming less popular because of the controversy surrounding the etiological role played by group A streptococcal infection in the disease. The term "acute neuropsychiatric symptoms of childhood " is a term circulating as a potential substitute for this diagnosis (CANS). There are several hypothetical causes of CANS , some viral, some toxic, and still some metabolic. Currently, there are no universally accepted standards for the treatment of CANS; however, a full examination is recommended, and empirical antibiotics are not needed.

participants ' OCD on their productivity was evaluated by the participants as having both good and negative characteristics. On the one hand, there were those who saw a decline in their academic and professional performance as well as an increase in absenteeism leading to inefficiency. Then you and all emails should be bold and then some emails should not be bold and then no, all emails should not be bold and finally bold, and color coded them.

4. Strategies for Coping with Stress and Anxiety

Throughout the study, participants developed unique strategies for adapting to, coping with, and ultimately accepting their circumstances. Self-talk, OCD, comedy, and keeping track of events and situations that may trigger other distractions were some of the strategies used (such as working, taking part in sports, talking to or talking to others). Participants had mixed feelings about the help provided to them. Some viewed the situation as positive, while others thought it contributed to an overall improvement in the quality of life of significant others, while others objected to the way it was managed. For example, some of the participants mentioned many people in their lives who offered them reliable support and proved extremely helpful in reducing the negative effects of OCD on their lives. They viewed the participant's family members as important sources of support, as family members supplied the participants not only financial but also psychological and emotional support, as well as ongoing reassurance and financial aid. Participants also described the important help they received from close friends, healthcare professionals, colleagues at work, and other members of support groups. Despite suffering from OCD, some of the participants were able to function socially and professionally with the help of humor, which was seen as a helpful gesture by these individuals. We used EST as a broad theoretical lens in trying to find the components that make up the participant's ecological systems. Our results provide a more in-depth examination of the participants' microsystems, namely the impact of OCD on a person over time, as well as in their daily lives and interactions with family members. The results of this study also provide an overview of the support options available to them as well as the methods participants used to manage with OCD. Our research is a sample of the expanding qualitative literature on OCD. This type of research uses exploratory methods to more deeply understand the perspectives of people living with OCD. . argues that it comes from his judgments about In addition, he claims that this method limits "intra-participant variation". The results of the current research highlight the variability of OCD and the importance of investigating different perspectives. These findings supply examples of consistent and contradictory explanations of the OCD experience. As a result of our findings, the participant realized that he had OCD. Our research has shown that initially people with OCD (and this feeling can often be traced back to infancy) believe their symptoms are normal. However, when the symptoms, in addition to causing great distress, began to significantly disrupt daily life and functioning, it was understood that the symptoms showed a pathological

or psychiatric problem, and the need to apply to the clinic arose. This was the case when the symptoms turned out to be causing the problem. For example, research has shown that those who suffer from OCD may not always fully understand the severity of their symptoms .

5. Simply a Bad Habit

OCD also have OC-like symptoms, the behavior is often considered normal or minimized as "simply a bad habit" that can be easily dealt with . This is because some people with OCD also experience OC-like symptoms . The importance of participants' awareness of their family members, particularly their spouses, that their symptoms are severe cannot be overstated. Compulsions proved by participants in the form of externalized actions such as checking or cleaning were necessary for diagnosis of the disease, as proved in the earlier study. On the other hand, research has shown that family members typically experience severe discomfort when watching OCD-related compulsions. In the context of OCD, interacting with important people has not always been viewed in a positive light by those affected by the condition. For example, Walseth et al. In their study of people living with OCD and their relationships in Norway, they discovered that patients often have the feeling that they are being watched and watched over by their partner. This was found in their study. This is a critical area for therapeutic focus to eliminate potentially persecuting actions of family members towards people with OCD and to aid individuals with OCD in reducing their frustration and disconnection from family members who do not understand themselves or their OCD . If this is not addressed, people with OCD and their spouses will avoid contact and behave in a confidential manner, Walseth et al. It is called "mental distance".

Our research has also shown that OCD can cause problems with daily activities. Our results, consistent with earlier research, revealed the significant impact of OCD on sleep quality, leisure activities, and interpersonal interactions of individuals with friends and family. Participants in our study had a tough time getting ready for bed because they had to constantly think about and perform their bedtime routines. Evidence that OCD disrupts sleep is inconsistent across research. Some people with OCD have trouble sleeping and associated fatigue, while others do not. The findings also included references to problems in daily functioning as well as general

physical and mental health, which is consistent with the hypothesis that sleep disturbance is the culprit.

Our study participants' judgments of the severity of their illness were aggravated by the sleep deprivation and accompanying repercussions, making it difficult for them to perform daily [50]. It has been shown that engaging in leisure activities can help survivors of mental illness and speed up the process. On the other hand, in line with the findings of earlier research, participants said that it was difficult for them to take part in activities they liked because many of these activities caused their OCD symptoms . Participating in recreational activities is not only fun, but also opens the door to new social opportunities. Therefore, withdrawal from these activities can result in feelings of alienation . Several participants noted the impact of their OCD on their participation and performance in school/university and/or employment , consistent with the findings of various quantitative and qualitative studies . The authors of this study found the topic "Failure in life" from their study of nine UK residents affected by OCD. They described this theme as the overwhelming impact of the situation on education and career. These people, like those in our study, reported that the disease caused their ambitions and aspirations to slow or suffocate.

This is also true for the participants in our study. As a result, people with OCD may experience feelings of helplessness and powerlessness because they are unable to live up to certain expectations or potential, which negatively affects their sense of self-worth. On the other hand, there is not much data to suggest that OCD has a beneficial effect on school or work, although it is briefly mentioned in two qualitative studies, including this study. For example, a study that commented on the comments of one of our participants found that it helped one with OCD to be meticulous and attentive to detail.

6. How They Cope With Interruptions That Are A Direct Consequence Of OCD

Our results also showed how individuals coped with interruptions in their lives that are a direct result of OCD. Participants concluded that receiving physical, emotional, and financial help from important people is essential to effectively manage and live with their OCD . The research reveals that perceived social support has a positive effect on an individual's ability to cope with the obstacles presented by OCD. This result is consistent with these studies. Like our findings,

there are many studies showing that most family members of individuals living with OCD adapt to them in many ways. For example, they can actively help the OC individual by actively helping them take part in rituals or doing chores to save time or reduce frustration . On the other hand, there is substantial evidence to suggest that the involvement and support of family members may worsen dysfunctional behavior. Although the people in our study made it noticeably clear that they value this type of adaptation and consider it a method of obtaining social support, other research shows that this type of adaptation hinders such adaptation. In addition, most of the participants had a positive impression of the aid provided to them by their families; however, there was some concern about the impact of the participants' illness on their loved ones. It could be argued that these concerns can cause people to avoid sharing, which can eventually result in a feeling of isolation . This notion is supported by the results of a recent qualitative study in which participants reported feeling disconnected from their family and friends. Therefore, a person's emotional reactions to family and friends can range from being grateful and happy to being a burden to worrying and walking away.

It is essential that researchers continue to explore this vital topic. As a matter of fact , there is evidence in the academic literature showing that including family members in the treatment process (for example, spouses in couple-based therapy) may not be suitable for everyone. Additionally, some studies have shown that family responses to OCD are altered and may be a cause of conflict in some cases. This can lead to worse relationship functioning, marital discord and divorce. The inability of patients to form meaningful relationships with other people not only limits their access to emotional support, but also makes them more likely to continue experiencing feelings of hopelessness and helplessness. Anxiety, anger, wrath, sadness, discomfort, and disgust were some of the intense emotional responses that participants in this study experienced because of their OCD , which they described as unpleasant, destructive, and inadequate. This is linked to diagnostic terminology such as the DSM and ICD, which define OCD as a condition defined by intrusive thoughts and compulsions with severe discomfort . This condition is known as obsessive compulsive disorder (OCD). Patients suffering from mental health problems such as OCD often experience a range of negative emotions such as anger, discontent, and hopelessness.

7. Various Strategies to Adapt and Stay Flexible

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Our patients have described several strategies for coping, adapting, and staying flexible with the challenges posed by their ailments and effects. Participants said that for the first time their OCD changed from trying to deal with oneself (problem-focused coping) to trying to resolve the emotions associated with their OCD (emotion-focused coping). This shift was recorded for the first time. Participants change their beliefs and views about their illness as they move from problem-focused to emotion-focused coping. As a result, they approach feelings of acceptance, which includes adopting their own terms and wanting to be accepted by others. This relative openness to the possibility of an OCD diagnosis is consistent with Relational Framework Theory (RFT), which forms the theoretical foundation of Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT).

The Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) approach is an experimental-based psychological intervention that aims to build resilience by combining acceptance methods with commitment strategies and behavior change tactics. A significant amount of research has been done on FUNCTION as both therapy and as a model for OCD spectrum disorders. The idea of acceptance and commitment brings us back to the first topic discussed in this research, "The realization of OCD." As said earlier, the impact on the participants' daily lives is clear and has an enormous impact on their relationships, regardless of whether they accept the diagnosis and the chronic nature of the condition. Patients suffering from OCD have a better chance of progressing in life if they can recognize the symptoms of their condition, stop denying or avoiding them, and accept the fact that they need therapy. Once people have this information, they can begin the process of accepting their diagnosis and its consequences. They may also commit to making necessary adjustments in their behavior, regardless of what is going on in their lives. This research suffers from several shortcomings . To begin with, the sample size is not exceptionally large, but still sufficient for comparison with other qualitative studies. Second, since each interview was a one-time event, the interviewer and interviewee had little chance of developing a relationship with each other. During follow-up interviews, there is a possibility that participants will be allowed to share information in more detail, by giving them a chance to feel more comfortable.

In conclusion, we agree that interviews with the participant's family members, friends, and co-workers can be used to gain a more in-depth assessment of the duality of OCD's impact on members of the participant's microsystem. This assessment can be obtained by collecting

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information from the participant. Interviews with these important people in the participants' lives will be an important avenue for added research that will go beyond the identification of individual-level issues that treatments need to address. Conclusion This in-depth qualitative study of the daily lives of people with OCD was able to focus on three main themes. These themes focused on participants' knowledge that they had OCD , the impairments produced by their symptoms , and how those symptoms were assessed and managed. According to the findings of this research, people suffering from OCD are likely to meet three main themes throughout their lives. Our findings were consistent with those found in quantitative studies, but our research adds a degree of depth that may be helpful in treating these patients. For example, the findings of the current research supply examples of coherent and contradictory narratives of the OCD experience. This highlights the importance of investigating the heterogeneity of the situation as well as individual perspectives. We also talked about how the patient's family and other important people should be involved in the diagnosis and treatment of the patient's problems . The results of this research brought to light the fact that these interactions are fluid and may not always be helpful; as a result, treatment must be approached with diligence and with a degree of flexibility. The need for acceptance was emphasized during a discussion on the management of OCD and the discovery of coping methods. This is in line with earlier research on the potential advantages of ACT , either as a treatment on its own or in combination with more traditional treatments such as cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) (CBT) . There are many nuances that still escape our understanding.

For example, it is not yet known whether experiences of living with OCD in South Africa differ significantly from experiences of living with OCD in other countries. This is something that is not yet understood. One such potential area of research that could be explored is how regional barriers such as limited accessibility, prohibitive costs and lack of information have an impact on the lives of people with OCD living in South Africa. The fourth tip is to look for other people who can help you. When you think you have no control over the situation and are completely on your own, this can make your OCD symptoms grow more severe. As you build better relationships with other individuals, your feelings of isolation and vulnerability will decrease. Even if all you do is talk to someone who knows you about your worries and aspirations, it can make them seem less threatening. It's important to maintain your connections with friends and family. Obsessions and compulsions can take over a person's life to the point where they isolate

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themselves from other people and avoid social situations. On the other hand, isolating yourself from other people will make the OCD symptoms you already have much worse. It is important for the person to do the necessary work to keep their connections with family and friends in good standing. When you talk to someone who is by your side about your worries and aspirations, it has the potential to make them seem less real and less scary. Join an OCD-related support group. Joining a support group for individuals with OCD can be helpful as it can be a constant reminder that you are not the only one dealing with the challenges posed by this illness. Individuals suffering from OCD can take advantage of the opportunities provided by support groups not only to discuss their own experiences but also to seek ideas from others who are dealing with the same challenges.

While stress is not the direct cause of obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD), it can bring on OCD symptoms or make already existing ones worse. Both physical exercise and direct eye contact with another person are effective ways to lower the level of activity produced by the nervous system. Additionally, you can instantly minimize feelings of anxiety by using movement and any or more of your body's senses (sight, smell, hearing, touch, and taste) to calm and relax yourself. You can try drinking a cup of your favorite tea, petting a furry animal, looking at a favorite painting or listening to your all-time favorite music. Relaxation methods should be applied. Using relaxation techniques such as mindful meditation , yoga, deep breathing, and other similar activities can be beneficial to your overall ability to reduce stress and tension levels, as well as to satisfy your cravings for unhealthy foods. If you want the best effects, you must make regular efforts to practice your chosen relaxation technique. Changing your normal routine daily can help relieve OCD symptoms . In addition to avoiding OCD compulsions, fears and anxieties, one of the most important factors in reducing anxiety levels is to lead a healthy and balanced lifestyle. Maintain a regular exercise routine. Your focus can shift away from your obsessive thoughts and compulsions when they occur using exercise as a natural and effective anti-anxiety medication that can help manage OCD symptoms . If you want to get the most potential benefit from your workouts, try to get at least half an hour of aerobic activity most days of the week. If you break up your workout into shorter ten-minute intervals several times a day and pay attention to the movement process throughout each segment, you can reap the same benefits as if you completed a longer session. Get enough sleep. Stress and anxiety not only lead to a lack of sleep, but not getting enough rest can make anxious

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feelings and thoughts much more intense. Anxiety and worry are two common factors that can contribute to insomnia. A healthy amount of sleep each night makes it much easier to keep your emotional balance, which is a vital part in the treatment of anxiety disorders such as OCD.

Avoid both nicotine and alcohol. While drinking alcohol may supply some relief from anxiety and tension, research shows that it worsens anxiety symptoms overall. Similarly, smoking may seem like consolation, but the truth is that nicotine is an immensely powerful stimulant. It has been shown without reasonable doubt that anxiety and OCD symptoms are worsened by smoking. Care and treatment of OCD, the most effective treatment for obsessive-compulsive disorder and often includes two components Cognitive-behavioral therapy : as described above, repeated exposure to the source of your obsession and response prevention are often included in the treatment. . Exposure and response prevention are often included in cognitive-behavioral therapy. Specifically, this aspect of therapy . Cognitive therapy is a type of talk therapy that focuses on a person's potentially harmful thoughts and an exaggerated sense of responsibility.

The goal of cognitive therapy for obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) is to teach patients healthy and productive ways to respond to obsessive thoughts that do not involve engaging in compulsive activities. This is the goal of treatment. Different methods for the treatment of OCD In addition to cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT), the following treatments are available for patients diagnosed with obsessive -compulsive disorder (OCD): Medication. In the treatment of obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD), a combination of psychotherapy and antidepressant medication is often used (OCD). On the other hand, treating symptoms with medication alone is rarely effective. Counseling for Families Family therapy can help increase awareness of OCD and reduce the number of conflicts that arise within families. This is helpful because OCD often causes problems in both social adjustment and family life. Two more benefits are encouraging family members and teaching them how to help a loved one battling OCD. Group Therapy or Counseling Patients receive help from the support and encouragement that group therapy provides, also by developing connections with other people coping with OCD, which helps reduce feelings of isolation .

just two examples of other OCD symptoms that may be used by some people as a coping mechanism to deal with the aftereffects of traumatic situations .

They discovered that the number of OCD-related visits during the epidemic was lower than in previous years. It is therefore essential that physicians conduct follow-up interviews with patients who have previously been diagnosed with OCD but are not currently receiving treatment for the disorder. Because the COVID-19 pandemic is not yet complete, it is highly likely that there will be an increase in the number of OCD cases after the pandemic ends. The severity of obsessive-compulsive disorder tends to increase in certain demographic groups as well as being influenced by personal characteristics. The clinical picture has become more consistent with 16 research publications on the impact of COVID-19 on people previously diagnosed with OCD prior to the outbreak. Most of these studies found a clinically significant increase in OCD symptomatology in people with the condition . However, there were a few articles that reported or did not report conflicting results (34, 40, 42-44). The findings of these studies suggest that the COVID-19 pandemic is a source of stress for many individuals suffering from OCD, resulting in an increase in the severity of OCD symptoms ; however, not all articles we could find during our research fully support this hypothesis. For example, in some patients presenting with clinical worsening of OCD symptoms , symptoms were only part of a larger clinical problem. This is so because OCD is a subtype of obsessive -compulsive disorder. Among all prespecified subgroups of OCD patients, those with compulsions related to washing and cleaning showed the highest impairment during the last outbreak. Stress caused by COVID-19 was also linked to higher OCD severity, according to the study, and OCD patients were shown to be more likely than other patients to have moderate to high stress, generalized anxiety disorder, and depression.

handwashing and contamination obsessions were the most common OCD symptoms saw. The results of these studies imply that the COVID -19 pandemic did not have an impact on a considerable number of features that make up OCD. At least, that's the conclusion one can draw for the general population. However, there may also be an increase in the prevalence of other mental health disorders. This not only shows that certain groups of individuals are more likely to be affected by psychological distress, but it also shows that the pandemic has affected all sectors of society. The results of many different studies on students and young people confirm this claim. These studies have concluded that, overall, COVID-19 has a multifaceted impact on mental health. While not all these studies pointed to an increase in OCD symptoms , one consistent finding from all of them was that teens' mental health declined. Pregnant and medical

professionals are more likely to show symptoms of obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) than the general population, according to the results of several studies.

Numerous studies have shown that pregnant women, as well as those working in the healthcare industry, have higher levels of anxiety and obsessive-compulsive disorder symptoms. These results highlight the need to provide health workers with proper working conditions and rehabilitation programs to progress towards higher psychological well-being. In addition, they emphasize that more attention should be paid to the mental health of pregnant women. In addition, the researchers noted that children and young adults are a vulnerable population. The results of some studies show a link between having a difficult and traumatic childhood and the development of OCD symptoms in adulthood.

8. Children and Adolescents

Children and adolescents, with or without obsessive-compulsive disorder, have the potential to experience immediate harmful effects because of bad experiences during the epidemic. This is especially true for young children and teenagers who develop obsessive-compulsive disorder at a younger age and come from families with a history of mental illness (85, 86). It was seen that the teenager, who could not be treated in the mental hospital, showed more extreme symptoms. These effects are linked to a significantly increased risk of long-term repercussions for affected people, and as a result, we believe the at-risk group needs further investigation and close surveillance. Even though the practice of basic hand hygiene was one of the first preventive behaviors consistently promoted by many national governments, none of the studies we discovered examined the physical effects of OCD associated with mandatory handwashing activities. Also, there are no studies investigating the physiological effects of excessive hand washing using antibacterial soap. Research conducted and published prior to the COVID-19 outbreak suggests that washing hands too often and for too long can lead to significant skin damage as well as hand eczema (94, 95). As a result, people who wash their hands excessively for fear of contamination often pose a significant challenge to dermatologists.

According to the results of some studies, recommending that patients practice adequate hygiene may give them a cognitive sense of justification. Additionally, research conducted prior to the current pandemic showed a link between OCD and difficulty falling or staying asleep. It is

possible to make this connection directly or indirectly through other mental health problems. These findings are consistent with what we found in research done during this pandemic. Having trouble sleeping may also be linked to OCD symptoms, according to this research. This link was seen during the current epidemic. We felt it necessary to include these case reports in our systematic review to show how the pandemic is affecting people who already have OCD. The six case studies that are part of our study supply examples of how people suffering from OCD may respond to their illness as the epidemic continues. In more than one of these studies, the severity of the symptoms experienced by people diagnosed with OCD was emphasized. Key symptoms were introversion, avoidance of certain meals, frequent hand washing and excessive disinfection of their environment.

9. Conclusion

People with the most severe instances of panic disorder also reported having suicidal thoughts or really trying to take their own lives. According to the results of earlier studies, people with a dominant pollution obsession and obsessive cleaning tend to show the highest suicide rates of all OCD symptoms. In each of the case studies, patients receiving care in healthcare institutions received help from a treatment approach that included both pharmacological and psychological components. However, these findings should serve as a warning that people with OCD should be checked more closely to avoid the possibility of major negative consequences on their mental health that the pandemic could cause. Two of the case reports described possible improvements in OCD symptoms during the pandemic. Conrad et al., five adolescent female patients with OCD took part in a trial of cognitive-behavioral group therapy without a control group over a 12-week period in the United States. The experiment was conducted in the United States. The duration of the trial was exactly twelve weeks. While these patients were provided with modifications, social support, information on OCD symptoms, and coping methods, they were able to recover and improve outcomes throughout treatment. Kuckertz et al. They described the many and varied experiences they had with eight inpatients with OCD. During the pandemic, most patients experienced a less severe manifestation of their illness, but none experienced a noticeable decline in their quality of life. It is important to note that in these limited interventions, patients who have close and sustained contact with healthcare practitioners have a higher resilience to the effects of the pandemic and are better able to cope with the challenges

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presented by the pandemic. On the other hand, patients who experienced an acute exacerbation of OCD symptoms were typically those who were diagnosed prior to the pandemic or who did not receive regular follow-up and support from their healthcare professionals. This is because these patients are more likely to have gone untreated for their condition during the pandemic. To begin with, 76 percent or 45 of the 59 studies discovered were of a cross-sectional design, and data for these studies were available in the first few months of the pandemic. Most studies used cross-sectional designs that resulted in the identification of statistical relationships rather than the ability to show causal links. It is important to consider the fact that several studies are preparing to conduct longitudinal monitoring of relevant populations . Further longitudinal research is needed to explore the potential long-term consequences of public health recommendations made in response to the COVID-19 pandemic on OCD symptoms . This data collection method is not as correct as other data collection methods such as formal clinical interviews and is more likely to lead to biased results. The fact that OCD patients were more likely to take part in some studies during the epidemic may have led them to overestimate the severity of their own symptoms , one study found. This hypothesis is based on the observation that people with OCD are more likely to volunteer for certain studies (36). In addition, an increase in OCD symptoms likely represents the real danger presented by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, and it is possible that the increase does not reflect the obsessive -compulsive tendencies of the general population as a whole. On the other hand, most studies (95 percent or 56 percent of 59 people) did not use a representative sample. In this study, we looked at studies focusing on various subpopulations identified as at risk during the pandemic . These subpopulations included people who had previously suffered from OCD, as well as children, teenagers, and women who were pregnant. However, we could not find any article specifically addressing the symptomatology of OCD in another high-risk group, the elderly . As a result, most of the studies analyzed for this project looked at OCD symptoms associated with contamination. Other types of OCD have received less attention. More research is needed on clinical symptoms that do not appear immediately . Most of our study shows that people with OCD have worsening of their symptoms , but that existing disorders may not have a detrimental effect on every individual. Due to the gradual development and self-expression of OCD, the period makes any outcome much more troublesome. Due to the acute nature of COVID-19 and the ongoing pandemic, we do not yet have long-term data on the possible consequences of the pandemic and the quarantines it brings. This is because the epidemic continues. Longitudinal, international and

cross-cultural studies are needed if we are to fill the important knowledge gaps that still exist today.

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